

STIGMA AND DISCRIMINATION A HURDLE TOWARDS HIV DISCLOSURE IN A WORKPLACE: EMPLOYEES' PERCEPTIONS IN THE DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT, MOPANI DISTRICT, LIMPOPO PROVINCE, SOUTH AFRICA

Thandy Shirley Mathebula

Department of Research Administration and Development, University of Limpopo,
Polokwane, South Africa

Marubini Christinah Sadiki

Department of Inclusive Education, University of South Africa, South Africa

This study investigated whether stigma and discrimination are obstacles to employees of the Department of Agriculture and Rural Development in Mopani District within Limpopo Province, to freely disclose their HIV status in a workplace. A qualitative research methodology was applied. A purposive sample of twenty participants (male=10; female=10; age range=18 to 65 years) was selected. The constructivism theoretical framework was used to navigate the study. Semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were designed to collect data. Data was audio-recorded and transcribed. Five themes emerged from the analysis: disclosure of HIV and AIDS status to a colleague, supervisor, employee assistance professional (EAP) and significant others; and attitude displayed towards HIV-positive colleagues. Perception of anticipated reaction towards disclosure of one's HIV status is a determinant factor of whether to disclose or not. This study investigates the effect of stigma and discrimination towards HIV disclosure in a workplace from the employees' perspectives in the Department of Agriculture and Rural Development, Mopani District. Limpopo Province.

Keywords: Disclosure, Discrimination, HIV and AIDS, Employees, Perception, Stigma

Introduction

The Joint United Nations Programme on HIV and AIDS (UNAIDS, 2023) report shows that numbers of new HIV infections and AIDS-related deaths have continued to decrease globally, bringing the AIDS response closer to achieving sustainable development goal (SDG) 3.3 of ending AIDS as a public health threat by 2030. Globally in 2022, out of the 39.0 million [33.1 million–45.7 million] people living with HIV, 86% [73%–>98%] knew their HIV status, 76% [65–89%] were receiving antiretroviral therapy (ART), and 71% [60–83%] were virally suppressed. Viral suppression enables people living with HIV to live long, healthy lives and to have zero risk of transmitting HIV to other people.

According to Statistic SA (2022) the number of AIDS-related deaths has generally declined — from 278 741 in 2007 to 85 796 in 2022. Access to antiretroviral treatment has changed significantly, altering the pattern of mortality over time. More recently, there has been a small increase in the period 2021 (87 915) and 2022 (85 796). The COVID-19 pandemic has hampered the ability of the health sector to extend life expectancy in South Africa in 2021. A slight increase in AIDS-related deaths is apparent in the year 2021, regardless of efforts to ensure ART rollout and better regimens of treatment. Equally, there is no sufficient progress in reducing HIV- and AIDS-related stigma and discrimination. The International Labour Law (ILO) Recommendation, 2010, prohibits discrimination in the world of work on the grounds of real or perceived HIV status (ILO, 2021). Discriminatory attitudes towards people living with HIV remain alarmingly common in all regions (UNAIDS, 2023).

In the face of numerous efforts to change public attitudes, the reality is characterised by deeply ingrained social prejudice, stereotyping and stigmatisation of people living with HIV and AIDS (PLHIV) (National Agency for the Control of AIDS, 2016; Oluwasola, Oshiname, Agofure & Oluwasola, 2017). In response to stigma and discrimination as a structural driver of new HIV infection, the HIV stigma index in South Africa documented three types of stigma, namely external, internal and anticipated (HSRC, 2014). External stigma is displayed through attitudes or actions aimed at PLHIV, including insults, rejection, intolerance, stereotyping, discrimination and physical violence, whereas internal stigma is the opposite in that PLHIV may

also experience self-blaming and shame. Regarding the latter, PLHIV anticipate that they will be treated differently or poorly because of the stigma attached to having HIV.

Experiencing stigma and discrimination in any form may result in the spread of new HIV infections. Rahman et al. (2023) infer that stigma and discrimination provide opportunities for the spread of the infection because, in order to avoid the unpleasant consequences of revealing the status, stigmatised persons may conceal their seropositivity from others, especially their sexual partners, thereby aiding the spread of the infection. Similarly, UNAIDS (2023) posits that stigma is discouraging people from seeking HIV prevention services, testing for HIV, starting and staying on HIV treatment. This practice undermines the prevention efforts aimed at attaining zero new HIV infections, zero stigma and discrimination and zero deaths by the year 2030.

Furthermore, Achwoka (2021) reiterates that the stigma and discrimination associated with HIV and AIDS are far bigger and considerably different from being diagnosed with non-communicable diseases such as diabetes, cancer and hypertension. This may be because HIV is primarily transmitted through sexual intercourse and people erroneously link HIV infection with sexual promiscuity. There is a dire need to achieve a transition whereby more employees willingly disclose their HIV status without fear of being stigmatised and discriminated against by fellow colleagues, employers and professional helpers.

Goal of the study

This study sought to explore perspectives of sampled employees on HIV and AIDS stigma and discrimination following disclosure of one's HIV status. Findings from this study could inform HIV and AIDS implementation strategies, as well as guide national and provincial policy structures in responding to social and structural drivers of new HIV infection, such as sigma and discrimination in a workplace.

METHODOLOGY

Participants and setting

A qualitative research approach, which was exploratory in nature, was applied in this study. Purposive sampling method was employed to select a sample of twenty participants (males=10, females=10) from the three municipalities within Mopani District, Limpopo Province of South Africa. The age of the participants ranges from 18 to 65.

Procedure and data collection

The Head of Department of the Limpopo Department of Agriculture granted the approval to conduct the study. The rationale behind the whole process was to inform the management about the purpose of the research project, give a description of the research design, the researcher's roles and responsibilities and, more importantly, to gain access as management has to grant permission. Wanof (2023). Similarly, the Turfloop Ethical and Research Committee granted ethical clearance (TREC number 32/2015: PG) prior the commencement of the study. Participants were approached about the study with an explanation of what the study was all about; how the information would be used and what was to be expected. No participant was forced to cooperate in the study; participation was voluntary. We safeguarded the privacy of participants as well as their identity by using pseudonyms to ensure anonymity.

An interview guide with a set of pre-determined open-ended questions aided to direct the face-to-face in-depth interview held at the participants' respective workplaces. Interviews were conducted in three dominant spoken languages in Limpopo Province, namely Sepedi, Xitsonga and Venda. The interviews lasted between 60 and 75 minutes. Handwritten notes and audio-recorded interviews were used to assist in capturing the data, which was later transcribed from the language of the participants to English. The transcripts assisted in carrying out the process of data analysis.

Data analysis

We followed the eight steps proposed by Tesch (in Creswell, 2009) to read all transcripts carefully to cluster and mark the topics as major, unique, and leftovers. The list of marked topics was abbreviated as codes, written next to the appropriate segments of the text. We checked if new themes and sub-themes were emerging. In doing so, the most descriptive wording for the topics was turned into themes. Topics related to each other were grouped to reduce the total list of themes. Data material that belongs to each theme was assembled in one place and a preliminary analysis was then performed.

Findings and discussion

The significant findings of this study revealed that stigma and discrimination were perceived as barriers to disclosure of one's status in a workplace. Disclosure or non-disclosure of HIV status is determined by the created meaning an individual attaches to the perceived world of reality (being HIV positive) after disclosure. The probability of disclosing HIV status in a workplace was assessed based on five themes emerging from the data analysis: disclosure to a colleague, supervisor, EAP, significant others outside the workplace, and attitudes towards an HIV-positive colleague. Themes were expounded and substantiated by direct extracts to give a voice to the views of the participants.

Theme 1: Disclosure of HIV status to a colleague

Some participants reiterated that they could reveal their HIV-positive status to their colleagues, while others mentioned that they could not. Yet others emphasised that they could disclose if certain conditions were met. Participants who choose to be open about their HIV status within a workplace do so for the mutual benefit of the infected employee and colleagues.

The following excerpts attest:

... In our sub-directorate, we are only four. In a case of an injury, it is important to alert them to take precautions when they assist me. (Participant C, female, 33 years old).

My colleagues should know and it will be an eye opener for them to take precautions in order to prevent the chances of the spread of the infection. It is hot now, if I can collapse here, they will not leave me unattended. They may assist to pick me up or provide any first aid measures. (Participant D, female, 58 years old; Participant G, female, 59 years old & Participant U, male, 55 years old).

My colleagues can assist me, may be in reminding me about the time of taking my medication. If I do not have a car of my own and something urgent came up that will need assistance with transport my colleagues will be able to understand the need for urgent intervention and assist accordingly. (Participant N, male, 39 years old).

However, a few participants consider disclosure to a colleague as remedial, whilst others maintain that good rapport with a colleague will be a determining factor whether to disclose or not.

Yes, I can in order to reduce stress. Talking to someone helps me to live well. I would not mind if my secret is divulged, it would be the problem of the one who breached the confidentiality. Myself, I would have achieved my ultimate goal of disclosing my HIV status and I will be stress free. (Participant F, female, 56 years old & Participant R, female, 36 years old).

Yes, I do not have any problem in doing that. People are afraid to come out, myself I do not care, people will talk today and tomorrow is another topic. It is like headlines in the newspapers. (Participant J, male, 33 years old).

It will depend on the trust and the nature of the relationship that we may have. (Participant L, male, 40 years old & Participant M, male, 48 years old).

The findings concur with the view that people who disclose their status will feel a sense of relief or that disclosure will send a message to others infected with HIV or affected by HIV/AIDS that open discussion and disclosure are safe (Twinomugisha, Ottemotter & Daniel, 2020). Mona (2013) agrees that having to ask for permission to

go to the clinic was not easy, as the participant had not disclosed to his employer. Some employees who are HIV positive and on treatment face a dilemma as they have to comply with their clinic appointments. If they have not disclosed, this becomes a challenge as they have to make up lies every time they have to go to the clinic. Some participants were not in favour of disclosing because of the negative consequences of disclosure.

The following statement relates:

No; the workplace is not a conducive environment wherein you can share your personal matters (Participant A, female, 39 years old & Participant I, female, 24 years old).

I cannot disclose to a colleague because they will spread the news that I am HIV positive. There is no guarantee that my HIV status will be kept safe (Participant Q, male, 56 years old).

No...employees are good in gossiping. You share such sensitive news with one colleague, the following morning the whole workplace will know. They treat you as if they care, but they stabbed you in the back when you are not around. (Participant B, male, 60 years old).

No, if I tell my colleague, I will even quit my job because they will spread the news, I will feel ashamed. (Participant T, female, 55 years old).

Idris, Crutzen and Van den Borne (2023) asserted in their studies that most of the participants believed that HIV and AIDS should not be discussed openly as it is regarded a private matter. Some participants in the study by the HSRC (2014) reported a similar fear of potential stigma, evidenced in being talked about, harassed, verbally insulted and physically assaulted. Wallace et al. (2023) cited that people living with HIV and AIDS were inevitably affected by the symbolic meanings attached to the disease. The later findings contradict Chapter 4, part 3 (55) (5) of the Public Service Regulations (2016), which stipulates that all employees shall treat information on an employee's HIV status or any other medical disease or condition

as confidential and shall not disclose that information to any other person without the employee's written consent.

Theme 2: Disclosure of HIV status to a supervisor

Like disclosure to a colleague, some participants perceived positive results in disclosing to a supervisor at the workplace if the environment is a safe, confidential and supportive one.

He supposed to support me in terms of sick leaves... it might happen that my sickness progresses up to the point where I fail to deliver some assigned duties.

It is my supervisor who will facilitate the provision of reasonable accommodation in case of disability due to my ill-health. (Participant B, male, 60 years & Participant R, female, 36 years old).

I can disclose my HIV positive status to my supervisor. If I keep it secret, I am aggravating the seriousness of my health condition. (Participant D, female, 58 years old).

I relate very well with my supervisor. She would be there to provide support in terms of all administrative requirements such as completion of sick leaves. (Participant G, female, 59 years old & Participant L, male, 40 years old).

If my supervisor behaves well, without harassing or even ridiculing me on my status; by harassing me I mean if he or she will not make funny comments about me like... ..she is doing this and that...because of the kind of sickness that she is having. (Participant C, female, 33 years old & Participant F, female, 56 years old).

There was consensus amongst participants that a good relationship with the supervisor prior to disclosure serves as a gateway for disclosing one's HIV status. Support and understanding are more anticipated in the event of disclosure. The Labour Relations Act 66 of 1995 protects employees against unfair labour practices such as pre-employment HIV counselling and testing. Employees who disclose their HIV status in the workplace should do so out of their own volition. Similarly, Open Society Foundation for South Africa (2009) posits that disclosure of one's HIV status may enable the employee to gain the necessary support from their employers and to access medical care. Likewise, Ayieko et al. (2023) found that the most popular

employees to disclose to were the supervisors so that they could allow them to comply with their clinic appointments. Many employees were forced by ill health to disclose, some needed support and others just wanted the freedom to choose what to do.

Some participants' expressions revealed their anger and emotions when they narrated their viewpoints about divulging their HIV status to their supervisor.

It is a no for the supervisor, unless they got into the ICU while I will be unconscious and read my hospital file. Other colleagues visit the hospital to come and see the condition so that they can spread the information at work. I will tell my mother that I don't want any colleague to visit me where I will be hospitalised...for me a colleague's telephonic support can be enough. (Participant A, female, 39 years old).

No...what applies to the colleague, applies to the supervisor. (Participant I, female, 24 years old, Participant P, male, 37 years old & Participant S, female, 47 years old).

I can't. The level of trust is not good. We only have a working relationship and personal issues are no go area. (Participant J, male, 33 years old).

To hell...even if the sun can rise; if I come to differ with her, she will use my HIV status to fight me back. (Participant K, female, 36 years old).

Concurrently, Toth et al. (2022) infer that trust is one of the critical elements considered before identifying whom to disclose to. The act of disclosure requires the trust that the HIV-positive individual will not be victimised, stigmatised or rejected after disclosure.

In most instances, negative feelings like anger, disappointment, self-blame and blaming others represent the feelings of internalised stigma. The results of self-reported feelings or internalised stigma were reported from a sizeable proportion of people living with HIV and AIDS who took part in the study by the HSRC (2014). Comparably, a study in Ghana on experiences and effects of HIV stigma revealed that the youth living with HIV experienced social and self-devaluation due to their HIV seropositive status (Kimera et al., 2020).

Theme 3: Disclosure of HIV status to EAP professional

Most of the participants in this study demonstrated confidence in disclosing to the employee assistance professional (EAP) for counselling, advice and moral support.

To the EAP professional...I can disclose my HIV status to them – but only because they are professionals. Truly speaking I am not giving correct personal information to service providers during wellness day activities. It is my strategy of protecting my image in case results do not go well. (Participant A, female, 39 years old).

Yes, I can. They can provide me with counselling and moral support. (Participant B, male, 60 years old, Participant D, female, 58 years old, Participant E, female, 55 years old, Participant G, female, 59 years old & Participant P, male, 37 years old).

EAP Professionals supposed to know in order to provide professional advises either to me or my supervisor when there is a need (Participant M, male, 48 years old, Participant Q, male, 56 years old & Participant R, female, 36 years old)

A few participants emphasised that disclosure can be done conditionally. Five participants attested:

EAP professional... you have to know what kind of person he/she is, and if you can trust them. When I want to tell someone confidential information, I start telling him or her false information and wait for two weeks to see if there won't be the spread of those news. (Participant C, female, 33 years old & Participant I, female, 24 years old)

It will depend. I have to apply my mind if really I need counselling. (Participant K, female, 36 years old). *Disclosure in this regard will be based on the assurance that the information shared shall be treated in confidence. I think I can need a professional guidance.* (Participant L, male, 40 years old).

Maybe I can, because I am not close to him or her. I would only need professional advise. (Participant S, female, 47 years old).

A similar finding was evident in the study by Borsa and Siegel (2023), wherein a community member was asked whether she had used a condom during her last sexual encounter. She replied in the affirmative, but a few days later, she confessed

that she had lied about her answer. Morgan (2022) confirms that some participants would prefer to disclose only under certain circumstances. Participants prefer to test the trustworthiness of the helping professional by narrating wrong information during the initial phase of the sessions. Similarly, The Global Network of People Living with AIDS (2018) asserted that people living with HIV should be able to choose the circumstances in which they disclose their HIV-positive status.

In this context, confidentiality of HIV status remains paramount because the negative consequences of HIV disclosure can extend beyond poor treatment in the workplace.

One participant asserted that he did not need any professional help because he could handle stress.

I am very strong emotionally, I do not think I will need counselling. I have a friend whom I can disclose and who have already disclosed his HIV positive status to me. I have supported him throughout the way and he is healthy and emotionally stable. (Participant I, female, 24 years old & Participant J, male, 33 years old).

Theme 4: Disclosure of HIV status to significant others outside the workplace

When people discover that they are HIV positive, one of the first steps is deciding whether to tell family or friends. Because of the stigma associated with HIV and AIDS and the potential for discrimination, people with HIV and AIDS have to be careful about whom they tell (Fauk, Hawke, Mwanri & Ward, 2021). It is evident in this study that there are significant others outside the workplace whom employees would prefer to disclose their HIV status to. Those are mainly their partners, children and parent(s), specifically a mother. It became apparent also in the study by Khan, Garman and Sorsdahl (2023) that participants carefully considered people to disclose their HIV status to. Sexual partners and spouses featured more prominently than any other individual. Disclosure of one's HIV status to a sexual partner or spouse is critical as it plays a major role in curbing the spread of HIV. Four female participants in this study also affirm:

Once I am done with counselling, I will only tell my partner and continue taking treatment. With the rest...I would rather keep it a secret until I die. (Participant A, female, 39 years).

I use to share my HIV test results with my husband; although he does not want me to go for HIV test but I go either. (Participant D, female, 58 years old).

I can disclose only to my partner, not even to my children, parents or whosoever. (Participant K, female, 36 years old).

... the first one to discuss with I am sure it will be my husband. The next person to share with is my mother. (Participant E, female, 55 years old).

Besides mothers, who were very popular confidantes, some indicated that they also disclosed to their children and siblings (Lightfoot et al. 2023). A study by Kabriku, Ansah and Hagan (2023) avows that the majority of the respondents disclosed their status to a family member, typically their mothers and/or their current partners. A male participant also concurs that he would prefer to disclose his HIV status to his wife.

I can disclose to my wife. We usually go along to test for our HIV status. (Participant B, male, 60 years old).

Okal et al. (2020) confirm that most men choose to disclose to their wives or partners, who are supportive and encouraging. The majority of the participants indicated that they had disclosed their HIV status to their husbands/wives/partners and to their children and affirmed that they felt empowered when disclosing their HIV positive status to the significant others (HSRC, 2014). No person lives in isolation. Everybody interacts with others, and what is of great significance is the perception of the interactions with people who are perceived as important and form part of the self (Freeman & Maloney 2021). Siregar (2023) affirms that humans cannot live alone. To envision life is to envision relationships.

Theme 5: Attitudes towards an HIV-positive colleague

The narrative below by some participants attests a positive attitude towards colleagues living with HIV and AIDS in the workplace. Care and support were shown by sharing meals and in terms of ensuring adherence to treatment. Participants attest:

Their attitude is good. They give necessary support to colleagues who are infected with HIV; they eat and live with them. (Participant A, female, 39 years).

In this office, we do support one another, some of our colleagues are on treatment and they are in a good state of health currently. (Participant B, male, 60 years old).

Evidence of positive relationships is evident in the reference below to a colleague who died of HIV and AIDS-related sickness.

I have just heard that there was an employee who passed away because of HIV and AIDS. The employees were concerned that the deceased would not have passed away if he/she followed the prescribed treatment. To me it meant that they care about each other. (Participant I, female, 24 years old).

Our colleague who is now deceased was never treated differently because of his HIV positive status, he was treated as the same colleague we had before the status. (Participant J, male, 33 years old).

Employees were also supportive to our deceased colleagues. I have not experienced any negative attitude to isolate our fellow colleagues. (Participant I, female, 24 years old).

State resources, such as vehicles and working hours, were allocated to visit a sick employee in order to send a message of care and provide emotional support.

One participant relates:

Employees were so very supportive to him (employee living with HIV infection). There was a time where he was hospitalised in Polokwane provincial hospital, government vehicles were authorised to transport some of the employees to Polokwane just to go and provide emotional support to our colleague. There was no gossiping, we have been taught that we treat people living with HIV and AIDS with respect and dignity. (Participant Q, male, 56 years old).

In distinction to the aforementioned narratives that indicated positive attitudes towards HIV-infected employees, some participants had different accounts.

I remember one colleague of mine was tested HIV positive during the period of my appointment. When other colleagues realised that we are working very close, they

called me in private and warned me that I must be careful because that colleague of mine is HIV positive. (Participant K, female, 36 years old).

Employees' attitudes were bad towards the colleague who was living with HIV. I remember they even stopped to put their water in a refrigerator. Now that colleague of ours is healthy because she is on medication, colleagues have accommodated her as one of them regardless of her HIV status. (Participant S, female, 47 years old).

I have witnessed what I am telling you (the researchers), two women colleagues were friends, they drink alcohol together, and sneak out of work together. One of them tested and told the friend who also came to me and asked that if someone is positive would I share a meal with her? The following week she stopped coming with lunch box because she didn't want to share with the HIV infected friend. (Participant T, female, 55 years old).

Implications for workplace stigma and discrimination

Employees living with HIV and AIDS have the same basic rights to health, liberty, autonomy, security and freedom of movement as the rest of the population. Stigma and discrimination associated with HIV and AIDS lead to violations of human rights, which fundamentally affect infected employees' wellbeing. At this developmental stage of the epidemic, some employees are still afraid to reveal their HIV-positive status. Workplaces are perceived as perpetuating stigma and discrimination through stereotyping, prejudice and gossip about fellow colleagues living with HIV and AIDS.

Such a working environment promotes lack of transparency, distrust, dishonesty and distress amongst HIV-positive employees. This negative human element may have a detrimental effect on the overall performance of workplace HIV and AIDS programmes, including distorted data and misinformed interventions. Employees may opt to remain silent about their HIV status and distance themselves from any activities regarding HIV and AIDS prevention. A successful workplace HIV and AIDS programme is the one that puts infected HIV employees at the centre of that specific programme.

It was apparent in this study that in a perceived stigma-free working environment employees feel at liberty to disclose HIV status to colleagues, supervisors and EAP professionals. The level of working relationship and degree of trust are determinant factors of whether to disclose or not in a workplace.

Limitations of the study and suggestions for further research

This study has explored and described the stigma and discrimination surrounding HIV and AIDS in the workplace: a perspective of employees in the Department of Agriculture, Mopani District, Limpopo Province, South Africa. The results of the study cannot be generalised to other contexts and settings. In view of this limitation, similar qualitative studies should be conducted in other workplace contexts in order to generate a broader and more comprehensive workplace response on HIV and AIDS stigma and discrimination amongst public servants.

Conclusion

We conclude that the decision to disclose or not to disclose one's HIV-positive status is based on the perceived outcomes of such disclosure. If non-stigma and non-discriminatory outcomes of disclosure are perceived by the one who discloses, the individual person is more likely to disclose their HIV status than the one who anticipates stigma and entrenched discriminatory outcomes. A good working relationship between supervisors and subordinates inculcates trust, acceptance and support when one experiences psychosocial challenges later in life. Upholding professional values, ethics and integrity at all times by all critical stakeholders creates a conducive working environment in which employees living with HIV feel liberated to disclose their HIV status without fear of prejudice, stigma and discrimination. Distrust and poor rapport between an employee and EAP professionals, health practitioners and peer counsellors may result in poor relationships, accompanied by disclosure of false information which leads to distorted intervention in addressing HIV stigma and discrimination in a workplace.

It is essential to contextualise HIV and AIDS workplace response by moving beyond an employee-focused to an employee-family-integrated approach. Forging a partnership with preferred significant others outside the workplace may yield positive results in preventing new HIV infection in a workplace. If employees refrain from disclosing their HIV status to anyone in a workplace, it should be inferred that there are significant others outside the workplace who assume critical supportive roles.

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